

INTRODUCTION OF ADDITIVE MANUFACTURING TECHNOLOGIES AS A TOOL FOR DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION OF LOGISTICS IN THE CONTEXT OF THE TRANSITION TO A GREEN ECONOMY

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Abstract. *The article reveals the role of additive technologies in the system of industrial supply of companies with material and technical resources. In the context of the global transition to a "green" economy, traditional production methods and logistics demonstrate high resource intensity, which is accompanied by the release of a carbon footprint various industries. It is proved that the use of additive manufacturing technologies in the logistics system is one of the key areas for the development of enterprises in various industries for the transition to a green economy.*

Keywords: *additive manufacturing, logistics, green economy, digital technologies, digital transformation.*

Introduction

Today, the energy sector is facing unprecedented challenges due to the need to decarbonize, improve energy efficiency and transition to circular economy models. Statistics from the International Energy Agency (IEA) show that production and logistics in supply chains account for up to 25% of global carbon dioxide emissions, which is contrary to the goals of the Paris Agreement and the concept of sustainable development as part of the development of a green economy [1]. Traditional subtractive methods of manufacturing components from renewable energy sources, such as machining or casting, are often accompanied by significant material losses (up to 90%), high transport costs and dependence on global suppliers [2]. These factors slow down the implementation of green economy projects, especially in remote regions where localization of production is critically important in terms of saving financial and time costs.

The introduction of additive manufacturing (i.e. 3D printing) technologies as a key tool for the digital transformation of logistics and industrial supply chains typically involves a shift from centralized supply chains to distributed print-on-demand solutions. The use of additive manufacturing technologies in combination with digital technologies not only reduces carbon dioxide emissions, but also optimizes the design of components to improve their energy efficiency.

The purpose of this work is to substantiate the role of additive manufacturing as a catalyst for the digital transformation of the logistics system in the context of the transition to a green economy.

Materials and methods

The source material for the study was scientific literature on the topic of the study, statistical data on the financial and economic activities of enterprises in various industries and open sources on the Internet.

Research methods: analysis of scientific literature, abstract-logical, system-structural, economic and statistical and modeling.

Results and discussions

Additive manufacturing technologies are a group of technologies used to build physical models, prototypes, tooling and functional parts based on three-dimensional computer CAD models or data obtained using 3D scanning. Additive manufacturing technologies in many practical areas today have advantages over traditional production methods [2].

Additive manufacturing is accompanied by zero carbon dioxide emissions due to the absence of dirty substances in the manufacture of products. Also, raw materials intended for additive manufacturing can be reused, which ensures waste-free production with the recycling of powder materials and gases [2].

Additive manufacturing is more energy-efficient than traditional manufacturing methods. Production processes account for 15% of energy consumption on the planet and up to 40% of global consumption of materials, so improving the energy efficiency and material intensity of production processes is one of the key factors in the sustainable development of companies in particular and the transition to the concept of a green economy in general. Additive manufacturing, as one of the key digital technologies that marked the transition of industry and the economy to Industry 4.0, has rapidly evolved from being used only for rapid prototyping of products to a tool for creating a high level of flexibility in production processes [1; 3].

Due to the ability to produce a wide range of small-sized material and technical resources, additive manufacturing increases the operational efficiency of repair and maintenance operations of technological equipment with lower energy consumption and increased energy efficiency of production operations, making the transition to a green economy more possible.

Due to the advantages of additive manufacturing, its use is justified, for example, in the oil and gas industry, potentially allowing additive manufacturing technologies to occupy a special place in the logistics as part of the overall digital transformation of business processes of oil and gas enterprises.

First of all, this is due to the remoteness of oil and gas fields from industrial centers, which increases both the logistics costs of the supply of materials and the delivery time itself. Equipment breakdown in the field can cause large financial losses per day. The frequency and stability of deliveries are an integral factor of efficiency in the organization of the industrial supply system. Often, there are no large warehouses with large stocks of spare parts on the territory of the deposits. This means that deliveries, in case of breakdowns and the need for repairs, must be made in the shortest possible time, meeting the criteria in terms of minimizing logistics and time costs.

Additive manufacturing has the potential to take a role in the logistics system as part of the trend of digital transformation of business processes. Placing additive manufacturing directly on the territory of production facilities can reduce logistics costs. Also, the time costs associated with the search for a supplier will be reduced by more than 10 times [4]. Oil and gas companies, being one of the largest sources of pollution, waste and significant carbon dioxide emissions into the atmosphere, adhere to the concept of sustainable development and the strategy of responsible consumption. Thanks to the zero waste of production and the recycling of raw materials, the introduction of additive manufacturing is justified and meets the trends of sustainable development, digital transformation and the transition to the formation of a "green economy" model.

Thus, it is possible to identify the main advantages of additive manufacturing in the context of digital transformation and the transition to a green economy:

- reduction of logistics costs;
- Reduced downtime during repair or maintenance
- reduction of production time;

- reducing energy consumption and increasing the energy efficiency of technological operations for the production of the required material and technical resources;
- reduction or minimization of the amount of industrial waste;
- recycling of raw materials for printing products on 3D printers;
- decarbonization of economic spheres;
- reduction of financial costs for obtaining the necessary material and technical resources;
- optimization of procurement activities;
- development of the company through digital transformation;
- attraction of additional investments with a potential increase in the value of the company's market capitalization;
- creation of new jobs with the involvement of highly specialized specialists in the field of 3D design;
- formation of technological sovereignty within the framework of the import substitution policy (applies to companies of the Russian Federation);
- development of a green economy and the concept of responsible consumption;
- creation of products with complex geometry;
- flexible conversion of production chains;
- low-cost small-scale production;
- accounting for localized needs;
- real-time customization through the use of additive manufacturing technologies in conjunction with other digital technologies of Industry 4.0
- optimization of warehouse logistics;
- acceleration of the NICR;
- use of alternative materials;
- availability of implementation for SMEs.

Conclusion

The introduction of additive manufacturing into the logistics system of companies is justified and is one of the key tools for the digital transformation of companies within the framework of the green economy. It reduces the carbon footprint of enterprises by minimizing waste by up to 90%, localizes production and uses recyclable materials. The introduction of additive manufacturing allows you to reduce the amount of energy consumed, increase the energy efficiency of production processes, optimize logistics and procurement, reduce equipment downtime, reduce financial and time costs, and reduce CO₂ emissions by 15-20%.

To realize the full potential of the introduction of additive manufacturing as a key tool for the digital transformation of logistics, cross-industry collaboration, improvement of the regulatory and standardization framework and increased investment in R&D are required. This will turn the additive manufacturing industry into a catalyst for sustainable development, combining both economic efficiency and environmental responsibility.

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